

ELECTROCHEMICAL INVESTIGATION OF PROCESSES OF COBALT ABSORPTION BY SOILS OF UKRAINE

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***Abstract.** Electrochemical methods of analysis are the simplest ones to operate, and highly sensitive and accessible for ecological control and measurement of mercury ions in soils. A method for measuring microconcentrations of cobalt in natural drinking water from water supplies, in soils, in surface water from lakes and wells, and in aqueous solutions by inverse chronopotentiometry (ICP) with high repeatability and accuracy in accordance with the criteria of metrological certification is developed in this study.*

The content of cobalt in soils is influenced by natural and anthropogenic factors. Natural factors include the geology of the territory, the age of soils, climatic conditions, the expansion of the organic fraction of the soil, wind erosion, which results in the distribution of minerals and atmospheric deposition of dust, which includes cobalt.

The mobility of cobalt in the soil is reversed to the rapid adsorption of soil colloids. Anthropogenic human activity also adds cobalt to the soil through three

mechanisms. The main of these are smaller amounts of cobalt also come to the soil from air transport. The average concentration of Co in soils in Europe is 1-20 mg / kg dry weight, and in the geologically rich in cobalt content areas such as North Wales, it can be significantly higher. For example, Paveley discovered a soil area where natural levels of Co content are more than 2,500 mg / kg of dry weight and this region has a healthy ecosystem that is adapted to such high concentrations of cobalt.

Cobalt plays an important role in plant nutrition, accumulation of chlorophyll, enhancement of the process of photosynthesis, increases activity of enzymes, which are catalysts of processes in plants. In plants Co is in the form of various organic compounds, most often cobalt-cuprum compounds. Cobalt is required to enhance the nitrogen fixation of bulbous bacteria), therefore it is most commonly found in legumes.

At present microfertilizers are used - $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_2)_2$, as well as fertilizers based on polyphosphates, phosphonitrile, phosphamide, and others. They have complex-forming ability. The study of their interaction with Co^{2+} ions is of considerable interest, since complex ions of cobalt, depending on their nature, strength and stereochemical characteristics, varying degrees of oxidation, have different mobility in the soil profile and availability to plants. The developed method of determination of mercury by the method of inversion chronopotentiometry allows one to maintain reliable ecological control of its content in soils samples of different natural origin in the range from 0.1 to 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dm}^3$, which corresponds to the regulated concentrations for sources.

Keywords: *Microelement cobalt, sorption processes, biohumus, humic compounds, soils, electrochemical pulsed method*

Introduction. The content of cobalt in soils is influenced by natural and anthropogenic factors. Natural factors include the geology of the territory, the age of soils, climatic conditions, the expansion of the organic fraction of the soil, wind erosion, which results in the distribution of minerals and atmospheric deposition of dust, which includes cobalt. Among anthropogenic human activities, which generally affect the local concentrations of Co in the soil, there is widespread agricultural use of lands and associated chemistry, the use of sewage sludge in the fields as fertilizers, the use of cobalt salts as a feed supplement for bovine animals, as well as air transport [1-5].

The mobility of cobalt in the soil is reversed to the rapid adsorption of soil colloids [6]. Anthropogenic human activity also adds cobalt to the soil through three mechanisms. The main of these are smaller amounts of cobalt also come to the soil from air transport. The average concentration of Co in soils in Europe is 1-20 mg / kg dry weight, and in the geologically rich in cobalt content areas such as North Wales, it can be significantly higher. For example, Paveley [7] discovered a soil area where natural levels of Co content are more than 2,500 mg / kg of dry weight and this region has a healthy ecosystem that is adapted to such high concentrations of cobalt. The maximum permissible concentration of mobile forms of cobalt in the soil is 12 mg / kg (X. Chulgjian et al., 1988) [1]. The part of land in Ukraine, which has very high content of mobile cobalt compounds, is 47.5% (7.9 million hectares), an average content of cobalt is in 21.8% of land area, and low content - 9% (1.5 million hectares). The value of the weighted average varies in the range of 0.15-0.86 mg / kg of soil.

Cobalt is found in soils in various compounds, the degree of availability of which for plants is different [1]. The soluble salts of cobalt, deposited in the soil, can be fixed due to the formation of insoluble oxides, sulfides, phosphates,

carbonates, etc. This leads to the fact that optimal standards for cobalt fertilizers may be inadequate in crop nutrition. The effectiveness of using complex and complex mixed fertilizers containing Co depends largely on the mobility of cobalt compounds and the stability to soil consolidation.

Concentration of cobalt in soils depends on the soil reaction (pH), the content of organic matter, clay and the cation exchange capacity [9]. Since cobalt forms persistent carbonate and hydroxydic minerals that are insoluble in water, most cobalt forms in the soil are not biologically available to plants [8], which adversely affects their development. Therefore, there is a need to add cobalt-containing fertilizers to the soil to ensure the full development of plants.

Cobalt plays an important role in plant nutrition, accumulation of chlorophyll, enhancement of the process of photosynthesis, increases activity of enzymes, which are catalysts of processes in plants. In plants Co is in the form of various organic compounds, most often cobalt-cuprum compounds. Cobalt is required to enhance the nitrogen fixation of bulbous bacteria (vitamin B12), therefore it is most commonly found in legumes [5, 10].

At present, in agrochemical practice, trace elements, integrated in complex compounds, are used. So, the use of chelatons of polyethylenepolyamineacetic acid has allowed to achieve success in the fight against lime chlorosis of plants [2]. The paper [3] shows a sharp increase in the flow of the trace element Co to the plants of vicia and oats due to high mobility of $[\text{Co EDTA}]^{2-}$ in the soil profile. Pre-sowing treatment of corn, sugar beet, cotton seeds with ammoniacal complexes of Co and Mn gave significant increasing in crop yields [4].

At present microfertilizers are used - $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_2)_2$, as well as fertilizers based on polyphosphates, phosphonitrile, phosphamide, and others. They have complex-forming ability. The study of their interaction with Co^{2+} ions is of considerable

interest, since complex ions of cobalt, depending on their nature, strength and stereochemical characteristics, varying degrees of oxidation, have different mobility in the soil profile and availability to plants. Chelates formation with organic polydentant ligands to a certain extent simulates many natural processes. Complexes of this type are fairly stable and can be used as self-contained microfertilizers or in combination with macro-components. Therefore, it is important to study the absorption of cobalt from different fertilizers by different types of soils.

Experimental. For studies of the absorption of cobalt by soils from complex-forming environments the soil samples from a layer of 0-20 cm were taken. Properties of the studied soils are given in the Table. 1.

To determine the cobalt in soil samples, the most easy-to-use, high-precision new electrochemical method of impulse inversion chronopotentiometry (IChP) [12] using the improved analyzer of heavy metal salts "M-XA1000-5" was used, the principle of which is based on the basic method of inversion chronopotentiometry (IChP method) [13]. The theoretical foundations of the method and the main criterion equation of IChP are presented in [14]. Measurement of cobalt content in soils was carried out in accordance with the methodology developed and approved by Ukrmetrteststandard [15].

Immediately before the measurement of cobalt, a background electrolyte was prepared, consisting of a solution A: (2M HCl + 0.1M NaSCN + 0.4M Na₂SO₃) and solution B: (4M NH₄OH) in the ratio A:B = 3: 2. In measurements, a 2-electrode electrochemical cell with an indicator golden solid-state electrode was used. Its working surface was sanded with calcium sulfate chemically deposited,

thoroughly washed with bidistilled water. As a comparison electrode, a chloride electrode was used, which was filled with a solution of 2M HCl.

Table 1. Basic physical and chemical properties of the studied soils (n = 5; P = 0,95)

Soil	Soil reaction, pH (H ₂ O)	Humus content, %	Cation exchange capacity, mmol/100 g soil
Chernozemic-Meadow medium loamy	7,8±0,2	4,75±0,15	27,1±0,4
Sod-Podzolic light loamy	5,1±0,15	1,95±0,11	9,4±0,3
Dark-Chestnut sodicity affected heavy loamy	8,6±0,3	5,15±0,12	25,8±0,2
Meadow sodicity affected medium loamy	7,6±0,2	4,98±0,16	27,3±0,4
Dark-Grey Podzolized light loamy	5,9±0,2	2,98±0,2	14,9±0,2
Sodic crust solonets heavy loamy	8,8±0,3	2,12±0,11	8,8±0,2
Chernozem Southern low-humus heavy loamy	8,0±0,2	4,12±0,09	31,8±0,2
Grey Podzolized light loamy	5,4±0,15	2,58±0,11	11,8±0,3
Chernozem Podzolized medium loamy	6,8±0,15	3,78±0,11	21,8±0,2
Chernozem Halpic medium loamy	6,6±0,15	4,18±0,09	29,8±0,2

Measurement of Co (II) concentrations in soil samples was carried out using standard additives in the concentration range of 1.0; 0.1; 0.01 and 0.001 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$. Graduating solutions at a concentration of 10.0 1.0 and 0.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$ were prepared by diluting standard solutions of Co (II) (MSO 0137: 2000, DSA 022.78-98). The electrolysis potential of Co on a gold electrode is in the range $-1.400 \div -10000$ V.

As an example (Table 2), the results of measuring the concentration of Co (II) in model solutions of different concentration ranges are given. It has been established that the method of determining the concentration of Co (II) by impulse inversion chronopotentiometry method according to the developed method can be used in a wide range of concentrations from 0.001 to 1.0 mg/dm^3 with high accuracy, the limit of absolute error of measuring the concentration of cobalt does not exceed ± 0.2 C.

Table 2. Measurement errors for Co (II) concentrations in model solutions (n= 5; P = 0,95)

Parameters of measurements		Co (II), determined by the results of measurements, mg/dm^3
Indicator	Concentration of Co (II) in solution, mg/dm^3	
The specified and measured concentration of Co (II) in the model solution, $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$	1,0	0,98 $\pm$ 0,08
	0,1	0,093 $\pm$ 0,006
	0,01	0,0089 $\pm$ 0,0005
	0,001	0,00082 $\pm$ 0,0001
Relative measurement error, %		2,0 – 18,0

The results of measurement of the Co (II) mass in the soil sample by the IICP method and atomic absorption analysis, the relative error of measurements, depending on the concentration, varies from 2 to 18% (Table 3).

Table 3. Comparison of the results of the measurement of Co (II) content in sod-podzolic soil by different analytical methods, mg/kg (n = 5; P = 0,95)

Ion	IICP Method				Atomic-Absorbtion Analysis			
	test 1	test 2	test 3	average value	test 1	test 2	test 3	average value
Co ²⁺	1,28	1,21	1,18	1,223± 0,002	1,31	1,24	1,16	1,236± 0,004

As a result of the studies, a sufficient level of coincidence of the results of measuring the concentration of cobalt in soil samples obtained by different methods of analysis has been established. The obtained data will satisfy the satisfactory accuracy and reproducibility of the results of the determination of cobalt under the proposed conditions, while the lower limit of determination of the element according to the developed method is set at the level of $1 \cdot 10^{-3} \mu\text{g}/\text{dm}^3$.

In the first series of studies, aqueous solutions of KNO₃, NH₄OH and (CSN₂H₄) were prepared, which are used as ligands in agrochemical practice. The experiments were carried out according to the following method: 10 g of air-dry soil was filled with 60 ml of a solution containing Co in the amount of 70 μg (at the rate of 7 mg/kg soil) and the corresponding ligand.

The mixture was shaken on a rotator for 1 hour and filtered through a folded filter. The filtrate was determined content of Co. Analysis of Co from solutions containing KNO₃, NH₄OH, and CSN₂H was performed using a new method of impulsed inversion chronopotentiometry [12–15]. In the second series of studies,

there were prepared solutions of polyphosphates $\text{Na}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$, $\text{Na}_5\text{P}_3\text{O}_{10}$ and Trilon B (disodium salt of ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid) as a universal organic complexone.

Due to the fact that the polyphosphate and trilonate complexes of Co do not regenerate on the electrode in the favorable potential range (up to -2.0 V), a special method of their analysis was developed. The method is the following: from 20 ml of a polyphosphate solution Co was extracted by 20 ml of dithizone in CCl_4 solution during 5 minutes at a pH of 8.8 (control with using a pH-meter "pH-150M").

The extract was washed with 10 ml of water to remove completely the phosphates and then the samples were evaporated on a plate in glasses to the state of wet salts. The wet residue was mineralized by adding 1 ml of conc. HNO_3 , 1 ml of 30% H_2O_2 and 1 ml of conc. H_2SO_4 . The contents were heated until sulfuric acid vapor appeared and then 1 ml of H_2O_2 was added again. Trilonate solutions were burnt in a muffle furnace without prior treatment with concentrated acid solutions. The residue was dissolved in 2 M NH_4OH and Co was determined by the IChP method [7, 8] using a gold solid electrode.

In the third series of studies, 100 g of biohumus was saturated with cobalt ions with an active contact of 0.5 M $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution for 48 hours. The solid phase was filtered, washed until negative reaction on NO_3^- ion, dried on the air. The obtained samples were used to study the extraction of cobalt ions from biohumus by solutions of 1M CaCl_2 ; 1M $\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$; 1 M HCl ; 0.02M EDTANa_2 + 0.09M NH_4Cl , which are wide spread in agrochemical practice for diagnostics of the movable cobalt forms in soil. Ratio solid phase:extractant was 1:10 by volume.

In the fourth series the biogumus was previously saturated by calcium ions. 100 g of biohumus were treated with 1M solution of CaCl_2 at shaking, filtered, the solid phase was washed with distilled water to negative reaction on calcium ions and dried in air. The obtained calcium-biohumus was used to study the specific adsorption of Co by humus in a solution of 0.01 M CaCl_2 . The experiments were carried out according to the regulations, as in the system: biohumus - 0,01M CaCl_2 - Co^{2+} .

Results and discussion. As a result of the experiments carried out by the above methods, the percentages of absorbed Co by various soils from various complexing media were calculated (Table 4).

The complexity of Co in all cases is close to 100%. In solutions of KNO_3 , NH_4OH and CSN_2H_4 , cobalt is a part of the complex cations $[\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]^{2+}$, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_n]^{2+}$, $[\text{Co}(\text{CSN}_2\text{H}_4)_n]^{2+}$, and in solutions of $\text{Na}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$, $\text{Na}_5\text{P}_3\text{O}_{10}$ and EDTA^{4-} anionic complexes $[\text{Co}(\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)_n]^{2-4n}$, $[\text{Co}(\text{P}_3\text{O}_{10})_n]^{2-5n}$, and $[\text{CoEDTA}]^{2-}$ are formed.

A high percentage of absorption of complex cations can be explained mainly by the cationic type of the soil absorbing complex of the main types of soils of Ukraine. With an increase in the size of ligands in the series $\text{H}_2\text{O} < \text{NH}_3 < \text{CSN}_2\text{H}_4$, the sizes of complex ions increase and, regardless of the soil specificity, the sorption effect decreases. Between the cation exchange capacity of soils and the absorption capacity of cobalt a close positive correlation was established, the correlation coefficient was 0.7976. Also, the absorption capacity depended on the content of humus in the soil, with the increase of soil humus content more mobile compounds of cobalt were found in the soil, the correlation coefficient was 0.7034.

Table 4. Absorption of Co by soils from different complexing media, %

Soil	1M KNO ₃ , pH 7,9	1M NH ₄ OH pH 11,8	1 M CSN ₂ H ₄ pH 7,6	0,15 M Na ₄ P ₂ O ₇ pH 9,2	0,25 M. Na ₅ P ₃ O ₁₀ pH 8,6	0,1 M EDTA pH 4,5
Chernozemic- Meadow medium	97,7	92,7	83,6	58,0	50,7	4,8
Sod-Podzolic light loamy	79,0	67,0	80,8	65,0	49,3	1,2
Dark-Chestnut sodisity affected	93,6	80,6	85,3	20,5	14,2	2,8
Meadow sodisity affected medium	97,6	95,7	89,8	62,5	62,5	7,5
Dark-Grey Podzolized light	89,7	92,6	95,5	51,3	43,6	6,9
Sodic crust solonets heavy loamy	88,1	97,9	89,5	48,1	43,0	4,8
Chernozem Southern low-humus heavy	98,0	88,0	88,6	50,0	15,5	3,1
Grey Podzolized light loamy	82,7	64,4	70,1	37,0	9,8	6,5
Chernozem Podzolized medium	97,3	93,5	82,1	58,4	55,0	4,8
Chernozem Halpic medium loamy	97,3	96,9	82,1	54,7	39,2	1,9

In the case of cobalt-containing complexes of anionic character, the sorption effect is a function of the strength of complex ions. Pyrophosphate complexes ($pK = 6.1 - 7.2$) and tripolyphosphate complexes ($pK = 6.6-6.89$) [9] are sorbed by soils

much more than trilonate, which is in accordance with high strength of $[\text{Co EDTA}]^{2-}$ ($\text{pK} = 16.1$) [10]. At the results of the experiment series 3 an assessment of the possibilities of biohumus as a carrier matrix of cobalt was carried out (Table 5).

Table 5. The amount of cobalt that has been converted into solution from biohumus (n = 5; P = 0.95)

Extractant	The amount of cobalt that has been converted into solution from biohumus, g/kg
1H CaCl_2	4,25
1M $\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$	8,35
1M HCl	22,50
0,02M EDTANa_2 + 0,09M NH_4Cl	16,18

In experiment 4, an analysis of isotherms of sorption or exchange of Co^{2+} on exchangeable ions of biohumus in the various solutions, which correspond to the isomers of the Langmuir monolayer adsorption, and hence are described by the equation:

$$a = \frac{a_m C}{A + C} \quad (1)$$

where: a , a_m – current and maximum adsorption of cobalt by a biohumus;

A – energy constant;

C – the equilibrium concentration of Co^{2+} in the solution.

By linearizing this equation with respect to the concentration, we have

$$\frac{c}{a} = \frac{A}{a_m} + \frac{c}{a_m} \quad (2)$$

Then present the experimental results obtained in coordinates $\frac{C}{a} = f(C)$.

From the fig.1 it is seen that the assumption of the Langmuir character of adsorption is well established. Thus, there is a high affinity of the Co^{2+} ions to biohumus both in its initial polyionic form and in the saturated by Ca^{2+} ions form. The growth of adsorption of Co^{2+} in a number of colloidal solutions of biohumus $\text{Ca} - 0.01\text{M CaCl}_2 < \text{biohumus} - 0.01\text{M CaCl}_2 < \text{biohumus} - 0.03\text{M NaCl}$ due to the greater ability of these ions to exchange on monovalent sodium ions than on two-valent ions.

Fig. 1. Isotherms of sorption of cobalt in the linear interpretation of the Langmuir equation

To estimate the specific sorption of cobalt by the biohumus, coefficients of selectivity (distribution) of the exchange reaction of cobalt ions with biohumus, saturated with calcium after [9] were calculated.

Since this process took place against the background of 0.01 M CaCl₂ in a large excess of calcium cations, the equilibrium constant was calculated assuming that the concentration of calcium ions in the solution remained constant.

$$K_{Co/Ca} = \frac{[Cobio.] [Ca^{2+}]}{[Cabiog.] [Co^{2+}]} \quad (4)$$

In this case we can also say that $K_{Co/Ca} = \frac{[Cobio.] [Ca^{2+}]}{[Cabiog.] [Co^{2+}]}$ K can have the same meaning as the stability of complex compounds [10].

Conclusions. The cobalt cationic complexes [Co(H₂O)_n]²⁺, [Co(NH₃)_n]²⁺, [Co(CSN₂H₄)_n]²⁺ - are almost completely absorbed by the soils. Anionic complexes – [Co(P₂O₇)_n]²⁻⁴ⁿ, [Na₅P₃O₁₀n]²⁻⁵ⁿ and [Co EDTA]⁻² — remain largely mobile in the soil profile. The sorption effect depends on the charge of complex ions, their strength, and also from the steric parameters of complex ions.

The use of complex-forming macro-fertilizers is perspective, in our opinion, not only to partially prevent the fixation of Co, but also from the point of view of its possible activation from fixed forms in the soil profile. A comprehensive study of the behavior of Co, depending on soil parameters and the physiological characteristics of plants, will greatly optimize the microelement nutritional process of plants. A high percentage of the absorption of complex cations of cobalt by different soil species is due to accumulation under the conditions of the chemical industry and the near humus. The tight positive links were established between absorptivity of the cobalt and cation exchange capacity (the correlation coefficient was 0.7976) and between absorptivity of the cobalt and humus content (the correlation coefficient was 0,7034). In the study of biohumus, it was found that in solution of 0.02M EDTANa₂ + 0.09M NH₄Cl, cobalt switches over to the

mechanism of competitive complexation, and its transition to epy HCl solution occurs due to protonation of the functional groups of the biohumus with which the metal is bound. The obtained results indicate that biohumus has relatively high sorption properties relative to cobalt and may be perspective for its use as an effective carrier matrix in various combinations with mineral fertilizers.

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